

EKMA ZA'FARON O'SIMLIGI NEMATODALAR FAUNASI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada Surxondaryo viloyatida iqlimlashtirilgan ekma za'faron - (*crocus sativus*) o'simligida aniqlangan nematodalar faunasining turlar tarkibi o'simlik organlari va rizosferasida taqsimlanishi tahlil qilingan. Natijada ekma za'faron o'simligining poya-bargida 13 ta, ildizida 51 ta, rizosferasida 61 ta nematoda turlari uchraganligi, shuningdek, aniqlangan nematoda turlari orasida: 6 turi dominant, 10 turi subdominant, 7 turi retsedent hamda 38 turi subretsedent turlar sifatida qayd etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: fauna, *crocus sativus*, nematodalar, rizosfera, dominantlik.

Abstract. The article analyzes the species composition of nematode fauna detected in acclimatized *crocus sativus* (*crocus sativus*) plants in Surkhandarya region, its distribution in plant organs and rhizosphere. As a result, 13 nematode species were found in the stem and leaves of crocus plants, 51 in the roots, and 61 in the rhizosphere. Among the detected nematode species, 6 species were dominant, 10 species were subdominant, 7 species were recedent, and 38 species were subrecedent.

Keywords: fauna, *crocus sativus*, nematodes, rhizosphere, dominance.

Kirish. O'zbekistonda dorivor o'simliklarni iqlimlashtirish va plantatsiyalarini kengaytirish, aholini tabobat yo'nalishi mahsulotlaridan foydalanishga adaptatsiya qilish bilan bir qatorda, ularning zararkunandalarini tadqiq etishga talab kuchayib bormoqda. Bu borada dorivor o'simliklarning biozararlanishini, keltirib chiqarayotgan va xo'jalikka zarar yetkazayotgan nematodalarning tur tarkibi va bioekologiyasini o'rganishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Tadqiqot materiali va metodlari. Dorivor o'simliklar namunalari 2020-2024 yillar davomida Surxondaryo viloyatining 4 ta hududlaridan: Termiz shahri, Termiz tumani, Sho'rchi tumani va Uzun tumanlariga qarashli ekin maydonlaridan iqlimlashtirilgan ekma za'faron o'simligidan 168 ta namunalari yig'ildi.

Namunalar yig'ishda marshrut metodidan foydalanildi [2]. Yig'ilgan namunalar, Termiz davlat universiteti Zoologiya kafedrasiga tegishli bo'lgan "Gelmintologiya ilmiy laboratoriyasi"da tahlil qilindi. Nematodalarni o'simlik ildizi va rizosferasidan ajratib olishda Bermanning "Voronkali" usulidan foydalanildi[5]. Doimiy preparat tayyorlash uchun Saynxorst metodidan foydalanildi[8]. Fitonematodalarning turlarini, jinsini aniqlashda N-300M Trinokulyar mikroskopidan, shuningdek, nematodalar aniqlagichlari va atlaslardan foydalanildi. Preparatlardagi nematodalarning o'lchamini o'chashda ko'pchilik tadqiqotchilar tomonidan qabul qilingan, Mikoletskiy tomonidan qayta ishlangan de Mann [6;7] formulasidan foydalanildi.

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Fitonematodalarni sistemaga solishda Chen va Hoddalar tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan nematodalar sistemasidan foydalanildi[1;3;4].

Tahlil va natijalar. Tadqiqotlarimiz davomida O‘zbekistonning janubida iqlimlashtirilgan ekma za’faron o‘simligi agrotsenozlarida aniqlangan nematodalari faunistik kompleksi keng doirada tahlil qilinganda, nematodalar tipining 2 ta sinf, 6 ta turkum, 22 ta oila, 36 ta avlodga mansub 61 turga mansub fitonematodalar qayd etildi (jadval).

jadval

Ekma za’faron o‘simligi va rizoferasida nematodalarning taqsimlanishi

№	Nematoda turlari	Individlar soni			Jami	100 %
		rizosfera	ildiz	barg-poya		
1	<i>Tobrilus kirjanovae</i>	5			5	0,16
2	<i>Mononchus truncatus</i>	13			13	0,40
3	<i>Mylonchulus sigmaturus</i>	16			16	0,50
4	<i>Dorylaimus stagnalis</i>	13			13	0,40
5	<i>D.bastianoides</i>	11			11	0,35
6	<i>Discolaimoides bulbiferus</i>	6	2		8	0,25
7	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i>	17	9		26	0,81
8	<i>Nygolaimus brachyuris</i>	6			6	0,19
9	<i>Plectus parietinus</i>	11	5		16	0,50
10	<i>Proteroplectus parvus</i>	7	2		9	0,28
11	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	66	33		99	3,08
12	<i>C.parvus</i>	22	13		35	1,09
13	<i>C.thermophilus</i>	11	3		14	0,44
14	<i>Eucephalobus oxyuroides</i>	51	27	2	80	2,49
15	<i>E.cornis</i>	13	5		18	0,56
16	<i>Acrobeloides buetschlii</i>	93	46		139	4,32
17	<i>Chiloplacus demani</i>	11	3		14	0,44
18	<i>Ch.propinquus</i>	103	62	8	173	5,38
19	<i>Ch.sclerovaginat</i>	98	57	4	159	4,94
20	<i>Acrobeles ciliatus</i>	4	3		7	0,22
21	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>	173	108	21	302	9,39
22	<i>P.subelongatus</i>	172	79	17	268	8,33
23	<i>P.longicaudatus</i>	45	24	2	71	2,21
24	<i>P.multidentatus</i>	28	43	12	83	2,58
25	<i>Mesorhabditis monhystera</i>	8	4		12	0,37
26	<i>Pelodera monhysteroides</i>	16	7		23	0,71
27	<i>Rhabditis brevispina</i>	180	77		257	7,99
28	<i>Rh.filiformis</i>	21			21	0,65

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29	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>	107	69	11	187	5,81
30	<i>A.eremitus</i>	31	14		45	1,40
31	<i>Aphelenchoides parietinus</i>	106	62		168	5,22
32	<i>A.dactylocercus</i>	8	4		12	0,37
33	<i>A.composticola</i>	50	73		123	3,82
34	<i>A.limberi</i>	8	4	1	13	0,40
35	<i>A.macronucleatus</i>	11	5	2	18	0,56
36	<i>Tylenchus davainei</i>	6	3		9	0,28
37	<i>Filenchus filiformis</i>	43	21		64	1,99
38	<i>Lelenchus discrepans</i>	23	7		30	0,93
39	<i>L.leptosoma</i>	7			7	0,22
40	<i>L.infirmus</i>	2			2	0,06
41	<i>Aglenchus thornei</i>	6	2		8	0,25
42	<i>Tylenchorhynchus brassicae</i>	23	15		38	1,18
43	<i>T.maximus</i>	17	11		28	0,87
44	<i>Bitylenchus dubius</i>	22	9		31	0,96
45	<i>Psilenchus hilarulus</i>	16	4		20	0,62
46	<i>P.clavicaudatus</i>	14	9	2	25	0,78
47	<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>	31	16		47	1,46
48	<i>H.pseudorobustus</i>	25	9		34	1,06
49	<i>Rotylenchus robustus</i>	27	12		39	1,21
50	<i>Pratylenchus pratensis</i>	58	24		82	2,55
51	<i>P.scribneri</i>	43	25		68	2,11
52	<i>Pratylenchoides crenicauda</i>	9	3		12	0,37
53	<i>Paratylenchus macrophallus</i>	4			4	0,12
54	<i>Hexatylus viviparous</i>	5	12	3	20	0,62
55	<i>Paurodontus gracilis</i>	11	5		16	0,50
56	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	64	33	4	101	3,14
57	<i>D.intermedius</i>	11	3		14	0,44
58	<i>D.myceliophagus</i>	20	11		31	0,96
59	<i>Nothotylenchus acris</i>	2	1		3	0,09
60	<i>N.exiguus</i>	5	3		8	0,25
61	<i>N.thornei</i>	8	4		12	0,37
Jami	Turlar soni	61	51	13	61	100
	Individlar soni	2043	1085	89	3217	100

Ekma za'faron o'simligi poya-bargida 13 ta, ildizida 51 ta, rizosferasida 61 ta fitonematoda turlari qayd etildi. Aniqlangan fitonematodalarning 6 turi dominant, 10 turi subdominant, 7 turi retsedent hamda 38 turga mansub fitonematodalar subretsedent turlar ekanligi qayd etildi. Shuningdek, eudominant turlar tadqiqotlar davomida uchramadi.

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Ekma za'faron o'simligi rizosferasidan nematodalarning 61 turga mansub 2043 ta individi topilgan bo'lib, ular orasida eudominant turlar qayd etilmadi. 6 turga mansub fitonematodalar *Chiloplacus propinquus*, *Panagrolaimus rigidus*, *P.subelongatus*, *Rhabditis brevispina*, *Aphelenchus avenae*, *Aphelenchoides parietinus* lar dominant turlardir. 10 tur fitonematodalar *Cephalobus persegnis*, *Eucephalobus oxyuroides*, *Acrobeloides buetschlii*, *Chiloplacus sclerovaginatus*, *Panagrolaimus longicaudatus*, *P.multidentatus*, *Aphelenchoides composticola*, *Pratylenchus pratensis*, *P.scribneri*, *Ditylenchus dipsaci* lar subdominant turlardir. 7 tur fitonematodalar *Cephalobus parvus*, *Aphelenchus eremitus*, *Filenchus filiformis*, *Tylenchorhynchus brassicae*, *Helicotylenchus dihystra*, *H.pseudorobustus*, *Rotylenchus robustus* lar retsedent turlar sifatida o'simlik rizosferasida aniqlandi.

Ekma za'faron o'simligi ildizidan 51 turga mansub 1085 ta fitonematodalar topildi. Ildizda aniqlangan fitonematodalarning 6 turi dominant, 10 turi subdominant, 7 turi retsedent hamda 28 turi subretsedentlardir.

O'simlik ildizida qayd etilgan turlar orasida *Panagrolaimus rigidus* (108 ta individ), *P.subelongatus* (79 ta), *Rhabditis brevispina* (77 ta), *Aphelenchoides composticola* (73 ta), *A. parietinus* (62 ta), *Aphelenchus avenae* (69 ta), *Chiloplacus propinquus* (62 ta) kabi fitonematodalar turlari individlari soni bo'yicha eng ko'p uchrovchi turlar hisoblanadi.

Ekma za'faron o'simligi poya-bargidan 13 turga mansub 89 ta fitonematodalar topildi. Poya-bargda aniqlangan fitonematodalarning 4 turi dominant, 5 turi subdominant hamda 4 turi subretsedentlardir. Tadqiqot davomida eudominant va retsedent turlar aniqlanmadi.

Xulosa. Surxondaryo viloyatida iqlimlashtirilgan ekma za'faron - (*crocus sativus*) o'simligining poya-bargida 13 ta, ildizida 51 ta, rizosferasida 61 ta nematoda turi aniqlandi. Nematoda turlari orasida: 6 turi dominant, 10 turi subdominant, 7 turi retsedent hamda 38 turi subretsedent turlar sifatida qayd etildi.

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